
Council
ON
Library
AND
Information
Resources

Annual Report 2001–2002

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The Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR) grew out of the 1997 merger of the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA) and the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over the years, CPA and CLR, in partnership with libraries, archives, and other information providers, advocated collaborative approaches to preserving the nation's intellectual heritage and strengthening the many components of its information system. CLIR was founded to continue this tradition of support for a national information system and a seamless web of information resources, of which all libraries and archives are a part.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2001–2002

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LETTER FROM THE CHAIRMAN

Stanley Chodorow
Chairman

The institutional form of the library is changing dramatically. Library users, both in academic institutions and in the community beyond the campus, are showing us what the information environment of the future will look like. On campus, faculty and students go to the library less than they used to, not only because the library has come to them but also because they have other sources of information. When users can get unmediated access to information and when they can find and use information anytime, anywhere, the old idea of the library first and foremost as a warehouse of information will disappear.

Library users today want access to information, regardless of where it is kept. For this reason, the future library will not simply be a modernized version of the current one. It is likely that few libraries will be able to survive in the traditional mode, that is, as independent entities that collect, organize, and provide access to information that they have acquired in one way or another.

Historically, librarians have not only collected and preserved the sources of information but also organized that information according to patrons' needs. In both academic and public libraries, the intellectual qualities of the librarian have guaranteed the quality of the collection and the guidance provided to it. As the library increasingly becomes one among many sources of information, it becomes more important than ever to develop the human capital of the library. The library of the future will be principally a human institution—a corps of information professionals rather than a repository or a treasure house of information.

This new vision poses many questions. What types of people should we recruit for the task of helping faculty, students, and ordinary citizens make sense of an increasingly complex information environment? How should these recruits be educated? How should the profession be organized, and how will it relate to the institutions that hire, promote, and pay its members?

This year, the Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR) has begun to explore these questions with the aim of providing guidance for the next phase of the revolution in information resources. Projects and programs relating to these questions will represent major efforts for CLIR in the coming years.

The membership of CLIR's Board reflects the organization's evolving activities and concerns. The range of perspectives and experience of Board members will be a significant asset as we refine our agendas for re-examining library education and other activities. Each year, a few members leave the Board and new members join. This past year, Elaine Sloan retired both from the directorship of the Columbia University Libraries and from the CLIR Board, on which she had served for six years. We are grateful to Elaine for her many contributions to our work. Billy Frye, chancellor of Emory University, retired from the Board after having served several terms on the boards of CLIR and the Commission on Preservation and Access. Billy's insights into the challenges and opportunities facing the library profession have been indispensable. We are pleased to carry on his legacy with the Frye Leadership Institute.

To build and broaden the Board's membership, we have appointed Norman Fainstein, Michael Ann Holly, Herman Pabbruwe, and James Williams. Norman Fainstein is president of Connecticut College. Michael Ann Holly is an art historian and head of research and academic programs at the Clark Art Institute. Herman Pabbruwe has many years of experience in commercial scholarly publishing. James Williams is university librarian of the University of Colorado and has a background in medical libraries. We are delighted to have these new members on the Board. Edward Ayers, historian of the Civil War and dean of the College and Graduate School of Arts and Sciences at the University of Virginia, will join the Board in the fall.

Collaboration with other institutions in the field has been especially important to CLIR's work this year; several examples are given in the section of this report devoted to programs. We look forward to continued cooperation with our partners.

On behalf of the Board, I want to thank CLIR's president and staff. Much of the influence that CLIR has exerted in national and international discussions and activities related to the acquisition, preservation, and management of information is attributable to their talent and dedication.

Stanley Chodorow
Chairman of the Board

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Deanna B. Marcum
President

CLIR's work is only beginning to reflect our consideration of the larger context of knowledge creation, dissemination, and use.

“**C**hin up” becomes the watchword of the Frye Leadership Institute each year. Richard Detweiler, Frye co-dean and Hartwick College president, opens the Institute with a presentation about the human tendency to keep our heads down, focused on the immediate tasks of the everyday. Leadership, he says, requires raising the chin and looking at the larger context. As the two-week Institute progresses, “chin up” is heard repeatedly. Participants use it to signal that the conversations have become bogged in details, and that it is more important to concentrate on the big picture.

The Council on Library and Information Resources has taken the “chin-up” message to heart this past year. Although we have long understood that the library is but one organization in the information landscape, it has always enjoyed a privileged position in our minds. But as we lifted our heads and looked at the broader context, we began to think more in terms of how information products and services as a whole will need to be configured if they are to have the greatest benefits for scholarship and society. We became aware that making the case for the library is related more to exploring and understanding the connections it must have to other information organizations than to asserting its unique qualities.

We then asked ourselves what must be done to ensure that the intellectual and cultural materials that support learning will be available to succeeding generations. We were humbled by the recognition that focusing exclusively on libraries would result in incomplete—and inadequate—stewardship.

PROJECTS REFLECTING A BROADER CONTEXT

CLIR's work is only beginning to reflect our consideration of the larger context of knowledge creation, dissemination, and use; however, three projects provide good examples of our broadening perspective and interests.

Understanding the User. In 2001, the Digital Library Federation (DLF) commissioned a wide-ranging study of information users. More than 3,200 undergraduate students, graduate students, and faculty members in liberal arts colleges and universities were asked not only about libraries but also about all sources they use to meet their information

needs. They were asked how comfortable they are with electronic resources and about where and how they do research, develop teaching materials, and prepare course work. The survey, which will be published this fall, produced hundreds of tables of data that CLIR is analyzing and making available for analysis by others. We hope that this information will help universities, libraries, publishers, and others in planning truly useful information services.

Preserving Digital Information. CLIR's work with the Library of Congress on its National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program, described on page 11, helped us appreciate the need to engage a wide array of educational, cultural, and commercial partners in documenting and preserving the products of human creativity. Films, television programs, radio broadcasts, and music, for example, are valuable economic and cultural assets that can be preserved only if commercial rights holders cooperate. Similarly, publishers, many of which are commercial enterprises, own the rights to many electronic journals. Because libraries license, rather than purchase, e-journal content, access to such content over time can be assured only if publishers are included in the consideration of how e-journals will be preserved and managed.

Commercial enterprises are not the only partners needed for cultural resource preservation. Librarians, archivists, and museum curators are the traditional stewards of intellectual and cultural content. Each group has developed standards and processes for carrying out its responsibilities. As these groups move into the digital arena, their practices become more similar and they confront many common problems. Increasingly, we are mindful of the need for collaboration as these groups develop digital collections and services for their constituents. Instead of competing for approval, libraries, archives, and museums must consider their collective role of stewardship and find ways to work together to identify, manage, and preserve resources for scholarship and human inquiry.

Collaboration and Outreach. CLIR joined with the Professional and Scholarly Division of the Association of American Publishers to form a Joint Working Group of Publishers and Librarians in February 2002. The group identified a series of topics that cause concern for both librarians and publishers, and then set out to develop projects to help solve some of the most pressing problems. For example, the group decided to compare results of user studies conducted by libraries with those of studies carried out by publishers to determine what changes may be required of both groups from the standpoint of user expectations.

Through *CLIRinghouse*, a publication launched in August 2001, CLIR tries to help university and college presidents, provosts, and chief academic officers grapple with information issues that exert pressure on higher education. After nine issues had been distributed to more than 4,000 administrators, CLIR conducted a reader survey. Results showed that readers are finding the publication helpful in thinking through information services and policies on their own campuses. CLIR plans to continue this outreach effort to administrators for at least another year. Many “library” issues need resolution, with administrative encouragement, through consultation and collaboration campus-wide.

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

The “chin-up” approach has also made us more aware of the need to think deeply about the education and training of information professionals, as Stanley Chodorow noted in his opening letter. Librarians are increasingly engaged in content development for teaching and learning. The CLIR Board devoted its May 2002 meeting to a discussion of the education and training of librarians and concluded that the distinctive educational paths for librarians, archivists, and museum curators need a new look in the digital environment. What are the common elements of their curricula? To what extent should internships and other forms of on-the-job experience be part of education for cultural resource stewardship? What do higher education and society at large expect of information professionals? These and related concerns of the broad range of information providers that include libraries will be at the center of CLIR’s agenda in 2003.

A BOW TO OUR SPONSORS

CLIR is most grateful to the institutions that contribute financial and intellectual support to our efforts. Each year, we ask institutions to help us address the problems we have jointly identified as important. We are especially appreciative of our sponsors in this time of economic and political uncertainty, when many academic institutions are under great stress. In 2002, 158 institutions supported CLIR as sponsors. Dartmouth College and Johns Hopkins University joined the DLF, bringing the total membership in that organization to 30.

We also enjoy generous support from several private foundations, government agencies, and individual donors. The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation provides greatly appreciated general support for CLIR as well as support for numerous projects. The Robert W. Woodruff Foundation is the primary funder of the Frye Leadership Institute. With funding from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, CLIR manages the international Access to Learning Award program. Funds from

The Atlantic Philanthropies, Documentation Abstracts, Inc., The Henry Luce Foundation, the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, and the H. W. Wilson Foundation have allowed us to pursue important projects described later in this report.

Grants from the Institute of Museum and Library Services have greatly helped our effort to identify business models for maintaining library and museum content on the Web and for beginning to redefine preservation in the twenty-first century. A contract with the Library of Congress has involved CLIR in the development of a national strategy for digital preservation.

Individual donors have been especially generous in supporting scholarship and fellowship opportunities. The A. R. Zipf Fellowship is awarded each year to a student who embodies the professional ideals of Mr. Zipf, a pioneer in information technology. The Patricia M. Battin Scholarship is awarded to a Frye Institute participant who is selected from an institution that cannot afford the tuition. This year, Mathilde and Howard Rovelstad established a fellowship program that will enable a student in a U.S. library school to take part in the annual conference of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA).

AND A BOW TO THE STAFF AND THE BOARD

The staff members of CLIR and the DLF are a devoted and talented group of individuals, each of whom brings special gifts to the organization. Each person is also fully committed to the mission of CLIR—to expand access to information, however recorded or preserved, as a public good. Their understanding and accomplishments are evident throughout the remainder of this report, but I take this opportunity to commend them for their fine work.

In 2002, Anne Kenney, a half-time director of programs at CLIR, was appointed assistant university librarian of instruction, research, and information services at Cornell University Libraries. Anne's official duties with CLIR ended on June 30, 2002, although she continues to be a wonderful colleague and collaborator. Former DLF Director Daniel Greenstein was recruited by the California Digital Library to become its new director in May. Dan has been an enthusiastic and energetic leader of the digital library movement. We are sorry to lose him, but know that he will continue to be involved in the work of CLIR.

Administrative Coordinator Scott Hunter resigned in May. New staff members joining CLIR this year are Alice Bishop, special projects associate; Arvaye Davis, administrative associate; Amy Friedlander,

special projects associate; and Amy Harbur, a library school intern from the Catholic University of America. In June, the DLF appointed David Seaman its next director. He began his assignment in July.

Finally, I extend bountiful thanks to the Board of CLIR—the new and continuing members, as well as those who recently left the Board after years of service. I am enormously grateful for the privilege of working with this dedicated and thoughtful group of individuals.

Deanna B. Marcum
President

September 30, 2002

THE PROGRAMS

RESOURCES FOR SCHOLARSHIP

CLIR's activities have been informed by a fresh look at the needs and aspirations of scholars working productively in both analog and digital formats. This year, CLIR has emphasized work that will help us better understand users and their needs.

Task Force on the Artifact in Library Collections

The work of the task force, which began in October 1999, concluded in November 2001 with the publication of *The Evidence in Hand: Report of the Task Force on the Artifact in Library Collections*. Members of the task force have since made several presentations to academic and library groups in North America. Discussions are taking place among interested parties on the creation of off-site repositories for imprints, a principal recommendation of the report, and efforts are under way to develop repositories of publications that are readily accessible online.

The task force report underscores the importance of preservation as a core activity of libraries at a time when many in the library and scholarly communities are asking probing questions about the role of the library in a networked research environment. Numerous user studies done in the past year, including research by JSTOR and a survey conducted for CLIR and the Digital Library Federation (DLF) by Outsell, Inc., have shown that preservation is a mission specific to libraries that is highly valued by faculty and students. The task force report also explored the question of whose responsibility it is to preserve scholarly resources. Although libraries are currently the locus of preservation actions, the task force concluded that responsibility for ensuring the preservation of original resources extends far beyond the staff of libraries and into the ranks of faculty, administration, and funders, and even to the public. The task force underscored the importance of engaging all these groups in the work of preservation. Raising awareness about preservation and finding ways to engage the necessary participants in preservation continue to be significant challenges for libraries.

Publishers/Librarians Joint Working Group

Changes in scholarly communication, largely the result of technology, have long created challenges for both publishers and librarians. In 1994, the Council on Library Resources and the Association of American Publishers launched a collaborative study of the potential impact of digital technology on libraries and publishing houses. The report urged the two groups to continue working together to understand the changes that were taking place and to launch pilot projects that would educate both librarians and publishers.

The need to work together is more urgent than ever. Recognizing that issues of intellectual property rights and journal pricing have kept librarians and publishers in separate corners, CLIR and the Association of American Publishers, Professional and Scholarly Publishing Division, agreed to create a Joint Working Group to find other areas of mutual concern in which to cooperate.

Two meetings were held this year. The group agreed on nine topics for further work, and projects are currently being formulated. Perhaps the most important result of the meetings was the decision to look at issues not from the publisher's or the library's perspective but from the vantage point of the information user. Libraries and publishers share the goal of making information more readily accessible to users. Likewise, both wish to continue to hold an honored place in the scholarly communication system.

The May meeting of the Joint Working Group focused on several user studies that have been conducted by libraries, publishers, and other parties. Representatives from these sectors presented their findings to the Joint Working Group, and projects have been designed to address common problems.

Creating a Test Database for Digital Visual Resources

What are the most effective methods for searching images? In an ongoing project to determine whether creating a large test database of images can provide answers to that question, Clifford Lynch, executive director of the Coalition for Networked Information, has developed scenarios depicting two approaches to developing the database. Under one approach, a massive and diverse image library could be built and made available to researchers. In the second scenario, a more topically focused database or databases, with high-quality metadata attached, could be constructed. Jennifer Trant, executive director of the Art Museum Image Consortium, is considering the feasibility of and likely next steps associated with each of the scenarios. She will produce a report of her findings.

2002 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Sinan Antoon, Harvard University, Arabic literature

Brenda Foley, Brown University, interdisciplinary studies (history, theatre, women's studies)

Christiane Gruber, University of Pennsylvania, art history

Angela Herren, City University of New York Graduate Center, pre-Columbian art history

Drew Hopkins, Columbia University, cultural anthropology

Susan Pearson, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, United States history

Alisha Rankin, Harvard University, history of medicine

Maria Rose, New York University, musicology

Natalie Rothman, University of Michigan, anthropology and history

Paula Saunders, University of Texas at Austin, anthropology

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships

In April, CLIR announced the first recipients of the Mellon Dissertation Fellowships for doctoral research in original resources. These fellowships are designed to enable humanities scholars early in their careers to spend up to 12 months in archives, libraries, museums, and other repositories (including private collections) to develop their research abilities. Fellows are also expected to identify and report barriers to resource accessibility by researchers. With funding from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation for a three-year program, CLIR this year awarded 10 fellowships of up to \$20,000 each to graduate students who are working in little-known collections, using primary sources in creative or nontraditional ways, or working in repositories that are not in a position to offer fellowships.

CLIR requires that fellows begin their program by attending a workshop on the use of primary sources. This year's workshop was co-hosted with the Library of Congress. The purpose of the workshop is to bring the fellows together with archivists and librarians to discuss research strategies, address any outstanding questions about how to work in libraries and archives, and enable the fellows to spend time with subject specialists who can advise them on relevant resources. At the end of the research period, each fellow will submit to CLIR a report that provides insight into the problems and possibilities that scholars encounter working in repositories.

PRESERVATION AWARENESS

The media of the twentieth century deteriorate faster than the media of other centuries, and the volume of materials that require stewardship is enormous. The task of keeping scholarly materials fit for use has grown so large, complex, and expensive that it can no longer be solely the responsibility of the library or archive. Preserving this resource base while also attending to the needs of digital information requires the informed cooperation of creators and publishers of information, as well as of budget officers, legislators, and assorted commercial entities.

Library of Congress/National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program

This year, CLIR provided support for a national initiative that addresses the long-term preservation of digital content. The initiative, mandated by Congress in legislation passed in December 2000, calls for the Library of Congress to lead a nationwide effort to develop a digital preservation infrastructure that will provide persistent, rights-protected access to digital content. The Library contracted with CLIR to organize key activities in the initial planning phase of this work.

The Library has done more than simply try to understand the technical issues associated with preservation. It has focused on reaching out to and involving a broad range of institutions, stakeholder communities, and organizations that may be new to traditional libraries and archives. New players come to preservation because they create and own the rights to content that will be crucial to understanding the cultural development of the nation and the world in the decades, or even centuries, to come. Much of this content is audiovisual and inherently digital; it is therefore especially vulnerable to loss.

CLIR's contributions have been to help identify people and institutions to include in discussions, write background essays, help bring to light important issues, and provide staff and publication services. CLIR also helped organize three sessions that brought together representatives from the broadcast, entertainment, commercial and noncommercial publishing, library, and research communities in the fall of 2001. Essays commissioned as part of that effort have been published jointly with the Library and released on both organizations' Web sites. As experts in digital library issues, CLIR and DLF staff members have frequently been asked to review commissioned work and to write background essays.

Preserving Web-Based Scholarship

With funding from the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, CLIR convened a group of scholars, librarians, technologists, publishers, and others to discuss the fate of scholarship created for and disseminated on the World Wide Web. An increasing number of scholars are creating sites comprising born-digital and reformatted information for a variety of purposes: teaching, research, even the creation of new primary source documentation about contemporary events. Most of these sites are developed outside the purview of a library or other institution dedicated to the stewardship of information over time, and they become obsolete before their potential value for scholarship can be assessed and action taken to preserve them. Many of these resources are created at great expense, supported or commissioned by foundations or federal agencies, yet seldom do funders demand or even expect that they be maintained for long-term accessibility.

Conference participants were asked to identify the emerging roles for traditional and new custodians of scholarship and primary source materials. A range of organizational models for preservation was examined, from JSTOR, Massachusetts Institute of Technology's D-Space, and the Internet Archive, to those of scholarly societies such as the American Geophysical Union and publishers such as Oxford University Press. The purpose of this activity was to see what functions of creation, organization, dissemination, and preservation can and should be assumed by various stakeholders in the chain of scholarly communication. In fall 2002, CLIR will publish a report that proposes some initial responses to the challenge of preserving Web-based scholarship.

The State of Preservation Programs in American College and Research Libraries

In fall 2001, CLIR initiated a study of what U.S. college and research libraries are doing to preserve their collections. Besides revealing what preservation activity is taking place at various institutions, the study aimed to identify which approaches work well and to learn how practitioners think national programs and organizations might help them improve their programs. The study was conducted in several phases and has involved the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data.

The study was done in cooperation with the Association of Research Libraries, the University Libraries Group, and the Regional Alliance for Preservation, and with representation from the Oberlin Group, land grant institutions, preservation educators, and the American Library Association. The work was carried out with support from the Institute for Museum and Library Services. Results will be published in fall 2002.

DIGITAL LIBRARIES

The digital revolution is transforming scholarship itself, along with the institutions that support that scholarship. Whereas digital development began as experimentation on the campus periphery, higher education institutions now increasingly incorporate it into their central services.

Because promoting the development, preservation, and use of scholarly information in digital form is a major part of CLIR's program, CLIR has housed the DLF since that organization's founding in 1995. The DLF coordinates its members' digital library research and development, identifies standards and best practices, and provides capital for creating tools and services that digital libraries need but cannot individually afford.

Evaluating Progress

The DLF conducted a major self-evaluation to assess the results of its first five years and determine whether it should continue operations. A DLF review panel, convened in July 2001, commissioned several studies of the federation's activities, including a survey of DLF board members and others who were in a position to judge the DLF's impact. In September 2001, the panel presented its report to the DLF Steering Committee. The committee accepted the review panel's finding that the DLF "has had a significant, positive impact on digital library development." On the basis of this finding, the committee voted to support the DLF's work for another five years.

Exchanging Ideas

As in years past, the DLF held spring and fall forums to give its members opportunities to learn about the latest digital library developments and compare notes on progress and problems. In November 2001, in Pittsburgh, forum participants focused on efforts to understand how people are using the digital collections and services now available and on what users will want in the future. At the spring 2002 forum, held in Chicago in May, participants concentrated on efforts to achieve "interoperability"—that is, on how to enable users to find and use collections and services managed by different institutions with different technical systems. These two concerns—establishing interoperability and understanding user needs—were also reflected in the following initiatives, which are among many that the federation advanced during the year.

Understanding Information Users

How is the digital revolution affecting scholars, teachers, and students in colleges and universities? Where and how do they now seek and use

information for research and course work? How do they perceive the campus library? What patterns of use are emerging?

To help answer these questions, the DLF commissioned a major survey from Outsell, Inc., a research firm serving the online information industry. In late 2001 and early 2002, Outsell conducted telephone interviews with 3,234 students and faculty members at nearly 400 colleges and universities. In fall 2002, CLIR will publish the results in print and on its Web site. To facilitate further analysis, CLIR will deposit the raw data with the Inter-University Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR).

Making Searching Easier

Any student or scholar trying to find digital information beyond a single institution must search across a complex set of independently developed computer systems. How can these systems be integrated? It will require, among other things, a means of access management—i.e., a way of controlling access to resources intended only for authorized users. In the past year, DLF members helped evaluate a possible way to meet that need in the form of a new protocol called Shibboleth, which supports access management across institutions. Simultaneously, the DLF continued its work with the Open Archives Initiative, which is testing a protocol for metadata “harvesting” to support in-depth searches of cataloging records for digitized material in multiple institutions.

Reducing Duplicative Effort

The growth of digital libraries has brought with it a need for information sharing to avoid redundancy. For example, digital library developers need to know whether a particular book or journal has already been digitized by another institution at a satisfactory level of quality, whether that book or journal is available to other institutions, and whether anyone is taking responsibility for its long-term preservation. Over the past year, the DLF convened a series of meetings to consider the development of a shared registry of digital reproductions and archival masters to record and provide such information. By year’s end, project developers had devised functional specifications for the registry. They are working with OCLC, which may serve as a host for the registry.

Changing Leadership

In June 2002, the DLF announced the appointment of David Seaman, formerly director of the Electronic Text Center of the University of Virginia Library, as the DLF’s new director. He succeeds Daniel Greenstein, who resigned to become university librarian and executive director of the California Digital Library.

LEADERSHIP

The library of the future will require information professionals who have both discipline-specific and technical skills. CLIR's leadership activities are designed to cultivate a large cadre of individuals who are prepared to work in collaboration with faculty and administrators to design information products and services appropriate for the new environment. CLIR believes that the next generation of leaders of information organizations must think and work in a fundamentally different way.

Frye Leadership Institute

In an effort to cultivate new leaders who are more mindful of the interdependencies of faculty, librarians, and information technologists, CLIR, EDUCAUSE, and Emory University launched the Frye Leadership Institute in 2000. The third class of the Frye Institute completed the curriculum in a two-week residential experience at the Emory Conference Center from June 2-14, 2002. The group included 43 participants selected from 130 applicants. Thirty-seven leaders in higher education participated as faculty.

During the first week, presidents, provosts, educational policy experts, and other administrative officers offered their views on the state of higher education today and the challenges confronting colleges and universities. In the second week, faculty, researchers, financial officers, library and information technology leaders, and training specialists addressed such issues as intellectual property and copyright, technological advances in

Frye Institute participants, June 2002.

Co-dean Richard Detweiler presents a Frye Institute certificate to Kathleen Kurosman of Vassar College. Looking on is Institute co-dean Deanna Marcum.

Frye Institute Participants, Class of 2002

Marianne Afifi, University of Southern California
Mary Beth Aust-Keefer, Edison Community College
Graham Black, Central Queensland University
John A. Blackburn, Jr., Washington and Lee University
Jane L. Blumenthal, Georgetown University Medical Center
Malcolm Brown, Dartmouth College
Robert M. Cotter, Xavier University
James M. Duncan, University of Iowa
Christa Easton, Stanford University Libraries
Daniel Gjelten, University of St. Thomas
Paul R. Hagner, University of Hartford
Brian Hoyt, Bucknell University
Cynthia A. Humes, Claremont McKenna College
Kevin Kane, Iowa State University of Science and Technology
Curtis L. Kendrick, Columbia University
Brett A. Kirkpatrick, The University of Texas Medical Branch at Galveston
Kathleen Kurosman, Vassar College
Wendy A. Lawrence-Fowler, University of Texas-Pan American
Paul M. Levit, Dickinson College
David E. Lewis, University of Rochester
Donna Liss, University of Nebraska-Lincoln
Timothy M. Logan, Baylor University
John Bert Lott, Vassar College
Daniel K. Marmion, University of Notre Dame
Peter McDonald, Syracuse University
Tracy Mitrano, Cornell University
Kathryn Monday, University of Richmond
Michael Nanfito, The University of Puget Sound
Michael Neuman, Georgetown University
Dale Peters, University of Natal
Frank T. Prochaska, University of North Carolina
Julia Rholes, University of Kansas Libraries
Gail Scanlon, Mount Holyoke College
Candice Scott, Schreiner University
David Starrett, Southeast Missouri State University
Toby Gail Stone, American University of Paris
Laurie L. Thompson, State University of New York Upstate Medical University
John Tombarge, Jr., Washington and Lee University
Lee Watkins, Johns Hopkins University
Jan Weller, Washington University in St. Louis
Susan Barnes Whyte, Linfield College
Irving Wiswall, Linfield College
BethAnn Zambella, Wellesley College

teaching and research, scholarly communication, and funding. In separate skill-building sessions, participants worked on enhancing their oral and multimedia presentation skills and personal leadership styles.

During the year, each Frye Institute participant will work on a practicum project on his or her home campus that involves collaboration with other information staff of the institution.

Nearly 150 librarians, information technologists, and teaching faculty from the full range of types of academic institutions have now completed the Frye Leadership Institute. The goal is to build a cadre of some 500 individuals by the end of the decade. This aspiration is reachable, thanks to the Robert W. Woodruff Foundation, which has generously provided funds for the first several years of the program. The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the Institute of Museum and Library Services, and the Patricia Battin Scholarship Fund also provide support for individual participants.

Academic Librarians Advisory Committee

The Academic Librarians Advisory Committee (ALAC) was formed in 2000 to advise CLIR about issues of particular importance to college and midsize university libraries. This year, the ALAC addressed three issues: the inclusion of electronic content and library services in courseware management systems; the changing role of public services in libraries; and the need for information on scholarly communication issues for presidents and provosts.

In January, the committee hosted a meeting of librarians, major courseware management system developers, and integrated library system developers, along with developers from the Open Knowledge Initiative and a representative from the Coalition for Networked Information. The meeting helped inform the group about enhancements being planned for courseware development and gave librarians a chance to share their views on software development needs from the perspective of content and services. Group members identified issues for further study and began to recruit libraries to undertake small projects that would facilitate inclusion of library-managed content and services in courseware. The group has identified two projects that will be initiated this year on two liberal arts college campuses.

The second area the committee addressed this year was the changing role of public services in libraries. After conducting informal research on other projects in this area, the group reached a consensus on the part of this issue it would like to address, namely, outreach and promotion of library resources and services.

In their effort to better inform presidents and provosts about issues of scholarly communication, committee members contributed to the development and evaluation of *CLIRinghouse*, described in the following section.

Outreach to Campus Leaders

Although CLIR develops many publications for librarians and other information professionals, it also seeks to provide insight and information for a broader audience—particularly leaders of colleges and universities. This broadened focus was taken at the request of campus librarians who wished to engage their presidents and provosts in issues raised by new information technologies but found busy executives hard to reach. In August 2001, CLIR launched *CLIRinghouse*, a one-page bulletin that provides, as its masthead says, “quick insight into information-investment issues for presidents, CAOs, and other campus leaders.”

Over the past year, with financial assistance from The H. W. Wilson Foundation, CLIR sent 10 issues of *CLIRinghouse* free of charge to about 4,400 executives and 2,000 head librarians in colleges and universities throughout the United States. The bulletins offered insight about such things as creating digital collections, preserving both digital resources and traditional collections, analyzing use of online materials, building portal services to facilitate use, integrating course-management computer programs with library resources, and evaluating digital information investments. More than 60 percent of the executives and more than 80 percent of the librarians who responded to a survey after the ninth issue said they wished to continue receiving *CLIRinghouse*. Accordingly, CLIR

plans to continue publishing the bulletin every two months for at least another year.

CLIR's president and staff published articles in several publications read by academic administrators and faculty members. Articles promoting attention to scholarly resource preservation were accepted by the *Chronicle of Higher Education* and by *Trusteeship*, the magazine of the Association of Governing Boards of Universities and Colleges. Two online periodicals—*D-Lib Magazine* and *RLG DigiNews*—published articles by CLIR staff. *EDUCAUSE Review* asked CLIR's president to become editor for two years of a new column about “e-content” that has been developed to help fulfill the magazine's mission to “explore the impact of information technologies on higher education.”

First Meeting of Chief Information Officers

Many small academic institutions are beginning to merge library and technology support into a single unit. Several leaders of such units expressed to CLIR their need for a place where their concerns could be treated as an integrated whole. In May, CLIR convened a meeting of 16 liberal arts college chief information officers to identify issues of concern related to organization, planning, and development and staffing. The meeting was productive, and CLIR will work with the group in the coming year to develop an agenda.

Zipf Fellowship

Miles James Efron, a Ph.D. student in information science at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, was named the sixth recipient of the Zipf Fellowship. Mr. Efron's research seeks to explain how statistical methods may be used to map information spaces to facilitate access to information. Mr. Efron's professional career has focused on research and development of information retrieval technologies for user-maintained digital libraries.

The Zipf Fellowship is awarded annually to the student in some field of information management or systems who best exemplifies the ideals of Al Zipf, the information science pioneer for whom the award is named.

Battin Scholarship

The third annual Patricia M. Battin Scholarship was awarded to Candice Scott, director of W. M. Logan Library and Information Technology Services, Schreiner University. The Battin Scholarship provides tuition for an individual who has been selected to participate in the Frye Leadership Institute, but whose institution cannot afford to cover the costs. The scholarship is made possible by contributions from friends and family of Patricia Battin, former president of the Commission on Preservation and Access.

INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENTS

CLIR’s mission—to expand access to information, however recorded and preserved, as a public good—is not bound by geography. Concerns about preserving digital data, providing affordable access to information, and training leaders for a changing information environment are shared globally. CLIR therefore continues to seek opportunities for cooperation abroad that advance these and other common agendas.

Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation Access to Learning Award

Colombia’s BiblioRed (Capital Network of Public Libraries) was honored with the 2002 Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation Access to Learning Award, which CLIR administers. BiblioRed was recognized for its success in providing free and innovative access to information for the citizens of Bogotá, particularly those in low-income areas. The library will use the US \$1-million award to expand its services.

El Tintal is one of three major libraries and sixteen local libraries that BiblioRed comprises. The libraries are strategically located throughout Bogotá to serve at least 70 percent of the school-age population and 40 percent of the adult population.

© Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation/Photographs: Douglas Robertson

The Access to Learning Award is given annually to a library or comparable organization outside the United States to recognize accomplishments in making information technology accessible to the public, particularly to underserved communities. CLIR, which began administering the award in November 2001, solicits applications. An international advisory committee of librarians and information technology experts reviews the applications and selects the recipient. More than 130 applications from 65 countries were submitted this year.

Web-Based Tutorial on Preservation and Conservation for Developing Countries

Work continued on a Web-based tutorial for preservation and conservation designed for use in Southeast Asia. The first of its kind, the tutorial is being developed under the direction of Anne Kenney and John Dean at Cornell University. It will cover three areas: management and planning, preservation, and building capacity. It will include self-assessment tools and a model for developing an action plan. Other features of the tutorial will be a glossary of technical terms, a vendor database, links to other sources, and a search capability. The tutorial is scheduled for release in fall 2002. CLIR expects to develop additional versions of the tutorial for other regions of the world.

The State of Digital Preservation: An International Perspective

In April, CLIR hosted the first in a new series of international symposiums that will address key issues in digital libraries, economics of information, and resources for scholarship. The symposium series, supported by a grant from Documentation Abstracts, Inc. (DAI), is called the DAI Institutes for Information Science. The inaugural symposium drew more than 150 participants from around the world to discuss strategies for digital preservation. A volume of conference proceedings was in press at the end of June.

Partnership with Mortenson Center

In 2001, CLIR became an official sponsor of the Mortenson Center at the University of Illinois, an organization that provides leadership training for librarians from around the world. The sponsorship offers a means for CLIR to extend its interest in leadership development to the international library community. Deanna Marcum and Anne Kenney presented leadership modules to librarians taking part in Mortenson Center sessions.

PUBLICATIONS

JULY 1, 2001–JUNE 30, 2002

MONOGRAPHS AND REPORTS

Selection and Presentation of Commercially Available Electronic Resources: Issues and Practices. Timothy D. Jewell. July 2001.

Building and Sustaining Digital Collections: Models for Libraries and Museums. August 2001.

Strategies for Building Digitized Collections. Abby Smith. September 2001.

Proceedings of the 2000 Sino-United States Symposium and Workshop on Library and Information Science Education in the Digital Age. November 5–10, 2000; Wuhan, China. D. E. Perushek, editor. 2001.

The Evidence in Hand: Report of the Task Force on the Artifact in Library Collections. November 2001.

Scholarly Work in the Humanities and the Evolving Information Environment. William S. Brockman, Laura Neumann, Carole L. Palmer, Tonyia J. Tidline. December 2001.

Usage and Usability Assessment: Library Practices and Concerns. Denise Troll Covey. January 2002.

Building a National Strategy for Preservation: Issues in Digital Media Archiving. April 2002.

CLIR Annual Report, 2000–2001.

NEWSLETTERS

CLIR Issues, nos. 22–27.

CLIRinghouse, nos. 1–10.

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David Seaman (*ex officio*)
Digital Library Federation

* indicates DLF Allies

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE IN FY 2002

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Archives and Museum Informatics Pittsburgh, PA	To prepare a feasibility study and implementation plan for creating a testbed for an image database	9/10/2001	\$21,000
Beagrie, Neil London, England	To produce an overview of international digital preservation initiatives	1/3/2002	\$19,370
Bennett, Scott Urbana, IL	To conduct a survey and write a report on reconceptualizing the academic library as a space for teaching and learning	2/25/2002	\$10,000
Besek, June Columbia University New York, NY	To write a paper on copyright issues involved in creating a digital archive	2/8/2002	\$5,000
Brylawski, Sam Library of Congress Washington, DC	To write a paper framing the issues in preserving digitally recorded sound	8/20/2001	\$3,000
Columbia University Press New York, NY	To convene focus sessions on accessing electronic publications	5/18/1999	\$20,000
Communications Development, Inc. Washington, DC	To help develop Web architecture for training tutorials on preservation	6/19/2001	\$26,250
Communications Office, Inc. Alexandria, VA	To conduct a survey in support of the Digital Library Federation review	8/3/2001	\$17,000
Cornell University Computing Science Department Ithaca, NY	To support Cornell University's work on the Open Archives initiative (OAI)	11/13/2000	\$177,467
Cornell University Office of Sponsored Programs Ithaca, NY	To develop a Web-based training tutorial on preservation and conservation for Southeast Asia	10/1/2001	\$124,886
D'Amato, Donald Falls Church, VA	To produce a paper on assessing the impact of image quality on digitized books and journals	6/20/2002	\$22,200
European Commission on Preservation and Access Amsterdam The Netherlands	To support the European School for Scanning's first program	12/11/2001	\$12,000
Flecker, Dale Cambridge, MA	To write a paper framing the preservation issues in electronic journals	8/20/2001	\$3,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Flecker, Dale Cambridge, MA	To write a background paper for a conference on archiving Web-based materials	2/1/2002	\$2,000
Flecker, Dale Cambridge, MA	To coordinate DLF projects during summer 2002	6/20/2002	\$5,000
Frischer, Bernard Los Angeles, CA	To write a report on new digital technology and the research library	6/18/2002	\$2,000
Harris, Pat NISO Bethesda, MD	To conduct a prestandardization study on a standard format for exchanging serials subscription information	4/21/2002	\$4,025
Ide, Mary Boston, MA	To write a paper framing the preservation issues in digital television	8/20/2001	\$1,500
IFLA The Hague, The Netherlands	To support the IFLA Core Programme for Preservation and Conservation	4/15/2002	\$20,000
Kirk, Elizabeth E. Baltimore, MD	To write a report on entrepreneurial ventures in research libraries	5/13/2002	\$2,000
Library Company of Philadelphia Philadelphia, PA	To support a conference on library history	3/1/2002	\$7,800
Lotze, Evie Kearneysville, WV	To develop a training component for the Mortenson Center Leadership Institute	10/16/2001	\$2,000
Lotze, Evie Kearneysville, WV	To lead a session on personal leadership styles at the Mortenson Center on June 26, 2002	6/21/2002	\$2,000
Lougee, Wendy Ann Arbor, MI	To write a report on the changing role of libraries in the digital age	2/12/2001	\$3,000
Lowell, Gerald R. Palm Springs, CA	To develop a personal leadership component for the international leadership program of the Mortenson Center	7/24/2001	\$3,000
Lowell, Gerald R. Palm Springs, CA	To conduct Phase I of the International Dunhuang Archive User Study	10/1/2001	\$6,070
Lowell, Gerald R. Palm Springs, CA	To support Phase II of the International Dunhuang Archive User Study	11/16/2001	\$50,000
Luna Imaging, Inc. Culver City, CA	To digitize images for the ArtSTOR Digital Bartsch Collection	2/1/2002	\$498,375

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Lyman, Peter Berkeley, CA	To write a paper framing the preservation issues in archiving the Web	8/20/2001	\$3,000
MacCarn, Dave Boston, MA	To write a paper framing the preservation issues in digital television	8/20/2001	\$1,500
Magnificent Publications Bethesda, MD	To document the meeting of April 23-24 entitled: "Preserving Web-Based Historical Documents"	4/5/2002	\$5,000
Moore, Carole Ontario, Canada	To report on digital archiving and provision of electronic resources to members of the academic community	5/30/2002	\$932
Mortenson Center for International Library Programs Urbana, IL	To support the International Librarianship Leadership Program	4/8/2002	\$20,000
OCLC, Inc. Dublin, OH	To conduct a study, <i>Assessing Quality in Digital Reference Services</i>	5/8/2001	\$24,000
Opal Publishing/Abaris Books Norwalk, CT	To assist in the digitization of images for the ArtSTOR Digital Bartsch collection	2/1/2002	\$221,050
Outsell, Inc. Burlingame, CA	To design a study to assess extent, nature, and use of scholarly information of students and faculty of universities and liberal arts colleges	7/12/2001	\$363,611
Rodgers, David Ann Arbor, MI	To write a report, <i>Business Analysis, Strategy, and Planning for Sustainable Web Access to Cultural Heritage Collections</i>	8/13/2001	\$12,000
Rodgers, David Ann Arbor, MI	To develop a business plan for the Frye Leadership Institute	1/15/2001	\$10,000
Romano, Frank Rochester, NY	To write a paper framing the preservation issues in electronic books	8/20/2001	\$3,000
Southeastern Library Network, Inc. (SOLINET) Atlanta, GA	To support a conference to establish collaboration between historically black college and university libraries in October 2002	6/24/2002	\$25,000
Southeastern Library Network, Inc. (SOLINET) Atlanta, GA	To support work on the competency guidelines for research librarians in the Southeast	7/28/2000	\$20,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Stam, Deirdre Syracuse, NY	To conduct a survey and develop case studies on the state of preservation programs in American colleges and university libraries	10/10/2001	\$26,000
Stenlake, Rodney New Haven , CT	To analyze possible licensing arrangements among digital libraries	9/30/1998	\$7,500
Wactlar, Howard Pittsburgh, PA	To write a paper framing the issues in preserving digital film	8/20/2001	\$3,000
Whiteside, Ann Visual Resources Association Charlottesville, VA	To develop a guide for standards in digital objects and images	1/23/2002	\$30,000

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

**FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

**FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2002
(With Summarized Financial Information for June 30, 2001)**

**WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT**

**STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia**

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

To the Board of Trustees
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, D.C.

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2002, and the related statements of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2002, and the changes in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The accompanying schedule of functional expenses is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Members American Institute of Certified Public Accountants

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2002

(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2001)

	Unrestricted	Temporarily Restricted	Total 2002	Total 2001
Assets				
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 944,938	\$ 755,461	\$ 1,700,399	\$ 689,245
Investments	-	7,005,631	7,005,631	6,345,110
Accounts receivable	-	108,328	108,328	-
Furniture and equipment, net	41,862	-	41,862	54,525
Other assets	<u>23,673</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>23,673</u>	<u>26,769</u>
Total Assets	<u>\$ 1,010,473</u>	<u>\$ 7,869,420</u>	<u>\$ 8,879,893</u>	<u>\$ 7,115,649</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets				
Accounts payable and accrued expenses	\$ 80,094	\$ 402,409	\$ 482,503	\$ 473,258
Capital lease payable	-	-	-	2,510
Sublet deposits	<u>2,956</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>2,956</u>	<u>2,956</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 83,050</u>	<u>\$ 402,409</u>	<u>\$ 485,459</u>	<u>\$ 478,724</u>
Net Assets	<u>927,423</u>	<u>7,467,011</u>	<u>8,394,434</u>	<u>6,636,925</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u>\$ 1,010,473</u>	<u>\$ 7,869,420</u>	<u>\$ 8,879,893</u>	<u>\$ 7,115,649</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2002
(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2001)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2002</u>	<u>Total 2001</u>
Revenue				
Grants and contracts	\$ 345,038	\$ 3,679,616	\$ 4,024,654	\$ 1,493,264
Contributions	252,437	1,370,001	1,622,438	1,739,870
Publication sales	13,119	-	13,119	14,238
Investment income	59,576	131,580	191,156	265,952
Other income	10,000	-	10,000	11,890
	<u>\$ 680,170</u>	<u>\$ 5,181,197</u>	<u>\$ 5,861,367</u>	<u>\$ 3,525,214</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions				
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 3,094,349</u>	<u>\$ (3,094,349)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 3,774,519</u>	<u>\$ 2,086,848</u>	<u>\$ 5,861,367</u>	<u>\$ 3,525,214</u>
Expenses				
Program services:				
Preservation	\$ 1,427,776	\$ -	\$ 1,427,776	\$ 807,468
Leadership	326,720	-	326,720	482,443
Digital libraries	1,594,469	-	1,594,469	669,746
Resources for scholarship	137,131	-	137,131	98,374
Economics of information	6,918	-	6,918	49,369
Total Program services	<u>\$ 3,493,014</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 3,493,014</u>	<u>\$ 2,107,238</u>
Administration	<u>610,844</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>610,844</u>	<u>531,342</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 4,103,858</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 4,103,858</u>	<u>\$ 2,638,580</u>
Change in Net Assets	(329,339)	2,086,848	1,757,509	886,634
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>1,256,762</u>	<u>5,380,163</u>	<u>6,636,925</u>	<u>5,750,291</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 927,423</u>	<u>\$ 7,467,011</u>	<u>\$ 8,394,434</u>	<u>\$ 6,636,925</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2002

(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2001)

	<u>2002</u>	<u>2001</u>
Operating Activities		
Change in net assets	\$ 1,757,509	\$ 886,634
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) in operating activities		
Depreciation	22,629	23,116
(Increase) decrease in other assets	3,096	7,051
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	(108,328)	21,000
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	<u>9,245</u>	<u>121,227</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Operating Activities	<u>\$ 1,684,151</u>	<u>\$ 1,059,028</u>
Investing Activities		
Proceeds from sales of investments	\$ 5,842,611	\$ 8,995,667
Purchases of investments	(6,503,132)	(9,892,925)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	<u>(9,966)</u>	<u>(43,005)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Investing Activities	<u>\$ (670,487)</u>	<u>\$ (940,263)</u>
Financing Activities		
Principal payments on capital lease	\$ (2,510)	\$ (2,630)
Net Cash Provided (used) By Financing Activities	<u>\$ (2,510)</u>	<u>\$ (2,630)</u>
Net Change in Cash and Cash Equivalents	\$ 1,011,154	\$ 116,135
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of year	<u>689,245</u>	<u>573,110</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of year	<u>\$ 1,700,399</u>	<u>\$ 689,245</u>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information		
Interest paid during the year	\$ 662	\$ 668

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2002

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council's operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2002
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs which include rent and other expenses are identified as support services costs and have been allocated directly to programs and administration. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2002 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

Summarized financial information - The financial statements include certain prior year comparative information summarized in total but not by net asset class. Such information does not include sufficient detail to constitute a presentation in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles. Accordingly, such information should be read in conjunction with the Council's financial statements for the year ended June 30, 2001 from which the summarized information was derived.

Reclassification of prior year information - Certain amounts from the prior year have been reclassified to enhance comparability.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2002
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Investments - The Organization has adopted SFAS No. 124, "Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations." Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2002

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ 5,360	\$ (6,370)	\$ 72,358
Corporate fixed income	249,396	(58,369)	4,107,589
Government securities	4,990	-	200,376
Certificate of deposit	11,267	-	100,368
Mutual funds	<u>79,324</u>	<u>(104,190)</u>	<u>2,524,940</u>
Subtotal	\$ 350,337	\$ (168,929)	\$ <u>7,005,631</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	<u>9,748</u>	-	\$ <u>1,700,399</u>
Total	\$ <u>360,085</u>	\$ <u>(168,929)</u>	

NOTE 3 - Income Taxes

The Council is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

NOTE 4 - Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

	<u>2002</u>	<u>2001</u>
Furniture and equipment	\$ 144,300	\$ 134,334
Leasehold improvements	<u>4,015</u>	<u>4,015</u>
	148,315	138,349
Less: accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(106,453)</u>	<u>(83,824)</u>
	\$ <u>41,862</u>	\$ <u>54,525</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2002
(Concluded)

NOTE 5 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 6 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council's contributions. The Council contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council's contributions were \$125,130 and \$116,525 in 2002 and 2001, respectively.

NOTE 7 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2002 and 2001, approximately \$637,065 and \$124,553 respectively, in cash equivalents was being held by a third party in a money market account that invests solely in United States government securities. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank at June 30, 2002 and 2001 exceeded FDIC insurance limits by approximately \$1,054,873 and \$527,012. Furthermore, all balances in investment accounts are uninsured.

NOTE 8 - Commitments

The Council has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August 2003. The Council is subleasing a portion of its space until August 2003.

Future minimum payments under all leases, net of sublease receipts, are as follows:

Year Ending June 30,	Operating Lease
2003	\$ 144,348
2004	24,166
Thereafter	-
Total	<u>\$ 168,514</u>

NOTE 9 - Accounts Receivable

	June 30, 2002
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 93,136
30 - 60 days	-
60 - 90 days	13,692
Over 90 days	1,500
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>\$ 108,328</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES

For the Year Ended June 30, 2002
(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2001)

	Digital Libraries		Economics of Information		Leadership		Preservation		Resources For Scholarship		Program Services		Admin.		Total	
	2002	2001	2002	2001	2002	2001	2002	2001	2002	2001	2002	2001	2002	2001	2002	2001
Grants	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -	\$ 26,666	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -	\$ 26,666	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -	\$ 26,666	\$ -
Refunds	-	-	-	-	(7,209)	-	-	-	(671)	(7,880)	-	-	-	-	(7,880)	(25,000)
Contracts	738,460	(8,000)	7,236	96,801	7,236	96,801	96,801	35,000	35,000	869,497	7,800	7,800	7,800	877,297	125,807	
Meeting & Travel	289,674	3,804	103,057	109,233	103,057	109,233	109,233	33,134	33,134	538,902	18,149	18,149	18,149	557,051	631,013	
Project Expenditures	2,475	-	-	412,137	-	412,137	412,137	-	-	414,612	-	-	-	414,612	-	
Communications	72,183	2,814	47,323	31,979	47,323	31,979	31,979	15,582	15,582	169,881	18,191	18,191	18,191	188,072	115,399	
Staff	406,255	8,300	108,961	664,203	108,961	664,203	664,203	52,012	52,012	1,239,731	297,244	297,244	297,244	1,536,975	1,311,010	
Consultants	67,746	-	570	67,941	570	67,941	67,941	-	-	136,257	23,827	23,827	23,827	160,084	108,531	
Program Support	17,676	-	66,782	18,816	66,782	18,816	18,816	2,074	2,074	105,348	227,207	227,207	227,207	332,555	328,919	
Board Expense	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	18,426	18,426	18,426	18,426	24,901	
TOTAL	\$ 1,594,469	\$ 6,918	\$ 326,720	\$ 1,427,776	\$ 137,131	\$ 3,493,014	\$ 610,844	\$ 4,103,858	\$ 2,638,580							

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.